

AUDIENCE ASSESSMENT OF THE COMPETENCY AND QUALITY OF THE REPORTING OF TELEVISION NEWS JOURNALISTS IN JAKARTA

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Abstract

The media is used for the benefit of party coalitions and the business world to cover up fraud and exploit the news conveyed. The government and media owners from political parties sometimes intervene in the press in conveying information so that the press can be controlled through agenda setting. Developing journalism competencies can create relationships between government and society. The research aims to analyze journalist competence influencing news quality and stakeholder assessments of the quality of news presentation by journalists in mainstream media (television). The research methodology uses mixed methods. The research population is the television news audience. The research sample was 240 journalists and 110 audiences. Researchers also interviewed media institutions and media observers. The test results stated that the competence of journalists influences the presentation of news so that the news broadcast has an impact on the audience and stakeholders. Highly competent journalists will produce quality news and have an impact on the audience. Journalists' professional competence, communication, mastering special media knowledge, and having a social orientation as a journalist have been assessed as competencies, except for research because it has been assisted by analytical technology in the era of digital technology. The presentation of news quality is not influenced by information needs based on the community's perspective. Based on the results of interviews with community representatives, managers, and administrators of independent and dependent media organizations, the low quality of news is due to; (1) intervention from stakeholders, (2) violations of the code of ethics occur due to intervention by the government and media conglomerates. (3) mainstream media tends to prioritize speed through mirroring online media, (4) non-online mainstream media (newspapers, television) which follow social media, (5) journalists do not do enough verification, (6) digital media technology problems, (7) the existence of business model built by the digital platform Google Adds which influences clickbait to get advertisements, (8) the proliferation of partisan media which refers to ideology, (9) media liberalization, (10) news quality is only measured based on the number of viewers, (11) young journalists lack of understanding of the Journalism Code of Ethics, (12) complaints from the public, (3) less attractive news packaging, (13) social media competition, (14) less in-depth news analysis, (15) the press is still going too far, (16) broadcasts violate moral norms, (11) liberalization of the media establishment, (17) lack of internal media coaching, (18) lack of creativity in the digital era, (19) hampered by the mindset of journalists who find it difficult to face rapid technological changes media, (20) lack of rewards.

Keywords: Agenda-Setting 2. Competence of Development Journalists 3. News Quality 4. Media Organizations 5. Stakeholder.

INTRODUCTION

Journalism practices in the world of television broadcasting affiliated with political parties tend to provide greater reporting space and intensity for the interests of certain political parties. The media has become a political vehicle for media owners, who are also politicians and businesspeople who adhere to the interests of legitimate groups and governments. Journalists under the auspices of editorial management sometimes dress up news content based on the "*interests of the customer*," following directions or obeying the orders of the media owner or manager. In fact, according to Potter (2001), the fact is that many television stations keep lists of problematic people, but the news does not touch them, so professional standards are neglected because it damage relationships between advertising clients and power, which can be detrimental to private media organizations. Journalists realize that they work in media owned by a conglomeration of politicians and businesspeople, which is structured hierarchically, making it difficult for journalists to assume professional responsibilities. The partiality of reporting toward the interests of certain groups by the media and its media crew does not reflect the impressive competence of its journalists. Capital owners interpret democracy as synonymous with freedom of action that is detrimental to their business, and obstacles to democracy are often associated with reporting transparency (Susanto, 2017).

Intervention from stakeholders causes the quality of the message to be weak, not objective, less factual, and biased towards the interests of the funding sponsor and the interests of the news rating or information substance. The power of media owners influences media content and has logical implications for society, so news coverage often contains the interests of market aspects and political elites. On the other hand, the government intervenes in the press's ability to convey information so that the press can be controlled to set agendas for these interests. This is the reason why television journalists, in carrying out their duties and roles, are often overshadowed by stakeholders who use the media to control economic and political conditions. The media as an agenda for political elites makes news a commodity to gain profits from these actions, and media owners can buy political influence (Valerisha, 2017). The media is used in the interests of party coalitions and the business world to cover up each other's fraud and take advantage of the news conveyed. The media and journalists in Jakarta seem to live under the shadow of capital owners, who are also political party administrators (Ritonga et al., 2019). The role of the news media is to achieve legitimacy and create positive perceptions in the eyes of society (Magnusson et al., 2021).

On the other hand, the government intervenes in the press's ability to convey information so that the press can be controlled to set agendas for these interests. This is the reason why television journalists, in carrying out their duties and roles, are often overshadowed by the interests of media owners from political parties who use their media to control economic and political conditions. Capital owners interpret democracy as synonymous with freedom of action that is detrimental to their business, and obstacles to democracy are often associated with reporting transparency (Susanto, 2017).

Apart from that, due to the competency problems faced by journalists, many media practitioners still do not follow professional training requirements. Many journalists oppose licensing journalists according to competency standards carried out by press institutions because they think it will be controlled and used by the authorities or government. Baran and Davis (2010) say that in large bureaucracies, it is difficult for journalists to assign responsibilities; lower-level journalists can claim to be just "following orders," and management-level journalists easily deny what is happening below them.

The country needs the presence of a press with clarity of perspective and a role in fighting information chaos or disinformation, which threatens democratic life due to the unlimited distribution of information. Development programs need to be socialized through the existence of mass media to fulfill the information needs of the community with notifications and developments on development projects, especially in the economic, health, state security, and improving people's welfare sectors. Communication and information play a strategic role by contributing to the interaction of different development factors, increasing the sharing of knowledge and information, and encouraging the participation of all parties (Servaes & Servaes, 2021).

Mainstream media journalists are expected to be able to maintain and have competence in carrying out their profession of mediating the interests of society and parties or political elite groups. According to Kovach and Rosenstiel (2004), the main task of journalists is to provide information to the public so that citizens can live freely and regulate themselves. Kovach and Rosenstiel (2001) emphasize that journalism plays a role in building society, fulfilling citizens' rights, and monitoring democracy running well. The journalist profession must maintain the prevailing press corridors to maintain and improve the quality of its reporting. In carrying out their duties, journalists must have adequate competency standards that are agreed upon by the press community. Journalist competency standards are important for producing quality news and development information. This journalist competency standard is to protect the public interest, people's personal rights, and the honor of the journalist profession. Providing quality press is only possible if quality journalist resources support it, and efforts to increase the number of knowledgeable journalists are the responsibility of each press practitioner (Bekti Nugroho, 2013). This journalist competency standard is to protect the public interest, people's personal rights, and the honor of the journalist profession. Competency standards are a measure of journalists' professionalism in protecting the public interest and people's personal rights, as well as maintaining the honor of the journalism profession (Waluyo, 2018).

This research highlights that journalist competence influences news quality and stakeholder assessment of the quality of news presentation by mainstream media (television) journalists in producing interesting news that is trusted by the public and is the fourth pillar of democracy in Indonesia. Lacy and Rosenstiels (2001) argue that journalists as a public space forum are part of the community's rapid participation to comment, provide criticism, and enrich information. Apart from carrying out his role as an independent power monitor, he also plays a role as a conveyor of public messages or public messages by adhering to journalistic and independent principles.

METHODOLOGY

The research uses quantitative and qualitative methods, namely a quantitative approach supported by qualitative data. According to Creswell (2014), mixed methods are a combination of quantitative and qualitative research approaches. The mixed method in this research uses a sequential explanatory strategic approach that is more inclined towards quantitative processes, followed by qualitative data analysis that is built on the initial quantitative results. Researchers place greater emphasis on quantitative methods, while qualitative methods are used to help explain or build on quantitative research results.

Researchers ask questions about the object of research to reach the truth. A qualitative approach is taken to explore important information that is not visible in quantitative measurements and confirm the results of quantitative findings. Researchers distributed questionnaires to journalists as analysis units and 110 television audiences as observer units. The results of the questionnaire answers from the audience are presented and processed using SmartPLS, and then narrated descriptively. Researchers ask questions to the audience (press institutions, society, government, business activists, politicians, and TV news viewers) as the unit of analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Influence of Journalist Competence on Quality News Presentation

The findings state that journalist competence has a significant effect on news quality. Journalists who have good competence will improve the quality of the news. The research results also show that journalists' competence in professionalism, communication, mastering special media knowledge, and having a social orientation as journalists has been assessed as competency, except for research, which has been assisted by analytical technology in the era of digital technology. The results of the analysis of descriptions of journalists' competencies from professional aspects, communication skills, special skills, and social orientation show that most journalists can carry out their profession well.

Journalists' professional competencies include (1) research; (2) selection; (3) writing scientific papers; (4) having insightful knowledge; (5) complying with the journalistic code of ethics; (6) identifying problems; and (7) using broadcasting equipment. To maintain professional competence, journalists state that they never work without doing research first. Journalists are used to researching to get accurate data on an issue, profile, or event, even though they are assisted by the Management Research Center (MRC). The audience responded that professional competence in adhering to the journalistic code of ethics in carrying out the journalistic profession needs to be well maintained. A code of ethics is needed so that journalists do not violate applicable press regulations and do not harm stakeholders.

In terms of selection, journalists never have difficulty editing scripts and videos while carrying out their daily profession. There are no difficulties for young to senior journalists because this skill is inherent in their field of work. Journalists also never have difficulty writing scientific papers in the form of technological innovations and chemical technology discoveries for

broadcast. The journalist's insight is also stated to have never experienced difficulties in obtaining information on scientific developments. Journalists adhere to the journalist code of ethics, stating that they never trade in the news so that the content is in favor of the payer. Journalists work by press corridors by not broadcasting pornographic news. Journalists also never have difficulty identifying problems in an event that occurs in society because they develop phenomena and research to obtain valid data to strengthen news writing. The ability to identify problems continues to be honed by seniors or editorial management so that young journalists continue to broaden their knowledge of various issues. Media involvement is a form of freedom to work but is still based on knowledge (Worth and Karaagac 2020).

Apart from that, television journalists do not have difficulty using broadcasting equipment because they have been trained through internal training institutions before being assigned to the newsroom and reporting. The results of the analysis show that few journalists have difficulty carrying out their competencies professionally. According to the researcher's observations, while working in the training department, the use of broadcasting equipment usually occurs in Generation X journalists due to inability and age, making it difficult to adapt to technology quickly. The problem of skepticism towards new technology is a dilemma for management as it tries to change the mindset of senior journalists belonging to Generation X.

Table 1: Respondents' assessment of professional competence

Professional competence	Very low		Low		High		Sangat tinggi	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Selection	7	2,9	1,8	7,5	84	35	131	54,6
Write scientific papers	8	3,3	18	7,5	102	42,5	112	46,7
Have insightful knowledge	9	3,8	64	26,7	87	36,3	80	33,3
Use of broadcasting equipment	3	1,3	28	11,7	111	46,3	98	40,8
Comply with the journalistic code of ethics	22	9,2	44	18,3	112	46,7	62	25,8
Identifying problems	11	4,6	6	2,5	14	5,8	209	87,1
Selection	2	0,8	18	7,5	88	36,7	132	55

Based on Table 1, it is known that the assessment of 209 journalists was categorized as very high in journalist competency, found in the indicator that journalists adhere to the journalistic code of ethics (87.1%), which states that journalists do not accept money from sources to write news according to orders, buy and sell news so that news content takes sides with the payer, and abusing the identity of the press for personal gain, broadcasting pornographic news and crime news that displays bloody images. The assessment of journalists' competence was categorized as very low and was found in the indicator that journalists said they had difficulty identifying events that occurred in society (0.8%), with the number of respondents being 2 journalists, meaning that journalists had no difficulty identifying problems.

Journalist communication competence in research discusses articulation, news that meets the needs of the community, and mastery of news material. Television journalists generally have no difficulty adjusting their intonation when broadcasting live so that the news can be heard clearly. Television journalists are usually provided with vocal training for dubbing and broadcasting. Apart from that, in the recruitment of prospective journalists, vocal and gesture

tests are one of the requirements for selecting television journalists. In the initial recruitment system, television management generally provides an on-camera test to see prospective reporters and presenters as one of the stages in selecting prospective television journalists.

Table 2: Respondents' assessment of communication competence

Communication competency	Very low		Low		High		Very high	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Articulation	8	3,3	21	8,8	90	37,5	121	50,4
News according to people's needs	29	12,1	37	15,4	80	33,3	94	39,2
Mastery of news material	17	7,1	23	9,6	76	31,7	124	51,7

Based on Table 2, it is known that journalists assess the communication competence of journalists in mastering news material (51.7%), with 124 respondents categorized as very high, while the articulation of communication competence is considered very low (39.2%), with the indicator being that journalists have difficulty making news according to society's needs.

In the special competencies of the media industry, mastery of understanding and mastering skills is also researched: (1) the editorial management system; (2) presenting news; (3) editing news; (4) compiling news rundowns; (5) analyzing data and facts; and (6) writing educational scientific papers.

Young, middle, and senior journalists generally have mastered the editorial management system, so it is not difficult to coordinate with the production team when sending videos to the head office. In the specific knowledge dimension of the media industry, it was found that journalists were less proficient in writing about educational scientific issues and rarely or did not know the news rundown.

Journalists have no difficulty conveying news because they master the material to be broadcast to avoid violating the journalistic code of ethics. Apart from that, journalists always write news according to the rules of journalistic writing, using the complete elements of 5 W + 1 H (when, where, who, why, what, and how).

In the era of convergence with technological advances, all news from various regions is provided and can be sent via an email newsbox designed by each television station. The use of broadcasting equipment usually occurs among Generation X journalists due to their inability and age, making it difficult to adapt to technology quickly. The problem of skepticism towards new technology is a dilemma for management as it tries to change the mindset of senior journalists belonging to Generation X.

Journalists convey news according to facts when presenting the news. For news editing, journalists edit the manuscript with structured and correct sentences to avoid mistakes. Journalists also stated that they had never had difficulty writing educational news in a scientific writing style.

Apart from that, social orientation is also considered in this professional competency, paying attention to news regarding (1) historical values, (2) moral values, (3) cultural values, and (4) scientific developments. In producing information regarding historical value, many journalists

stated that they never had difficulty collecting data for writing the news. In conveying moral messages, journalists admit that they always broadcast news that maintains the morality of the Indonesian nation. Journalists also strive to always present news that encourages people to care about preserving the eastern traditions of the Indonesian people. News broadcasts regarding the discovery of biological weapons are always presented to present developments in science.

Table 3: Respondents' assessment of specific knowledge of the media industry

Media industry-specific competencies	Very low		Low		High		Very high	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Analyze data, facts	9	3,8	5	2,1	54	22,5	172	71
Writing educational scientific papers	5	2,1	25	10,4	94	39,2	116	48,3
Compile a news rundown	10	4,2	18	7,5	85	35,4	127	52,9
News presentation	5	2,1	10	4,2	52	21,7	173	72,1
News Editing	4	1,7	7	2,9	75	31,3	154	64,2
Editorial management system	3	1,3	7	2,9	73	30,4	157	65,4

Based on Table 3, it is known that the competence of industry-specific journalists in the editorial management system indicator is known to be very few or only 3 journalists (1.3%), meaning that journalists have never made mistakes in work procedures, understand work mechanisms, and have no problems coordinating with the team. In assessing the competency of journalists in the very high category, it was found that in the indicator of writing scientific papers, journalists had difficulty writing news about developments in the world of education in the style of scientific writing.

Based on Table 4, it is known that journalists assess competence towards social orientation, on the moral value indicator (71.3%) with a total of 172 respondents. In the very low category of journalist competency assessment with 3 journalists as respondents, it is found on the historical value indicator (45.4%) that Journalists have no difficulty writing about the discovery of historical sites, even though they don't get much attention from the public.

Table 4: Respondents' assessment of orientation

Social orientation competencies	Very low		Low		High		Very high	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Culture value	6	2,5	10	4,2	66	27,5	158	65,8
Moral values	5	2,1	8	3,3	56	23,3	171	71,3
Historical value	5	2,1	24	10	102	42,5	109	45,4
Development of science	3	1,3	11	4,6	84	35	142	59,2

The competence of a television journalist must be to be able to produce journalistic work as a reference for the truth of information. In fact, according to Potter (2001), it was revealed that many television stations kept lists of problematic people who were not touched by the news so that professional standards were neglected because it could endanger the relationship between advertising clients and power, which could be detrimental to private media organizations. In addition, journalistic competence should not be reduced only to cognitive tasks (knowledge and skills); it is also necessary to take into account the ability to communicate, negotiate, build

trusting relationships, and interpret situations. This competency requires support from profit and non-profit media organizations, including the Ministry of Communication and Information of the Republic of Indonesia, to practice journalism knowledge in real terms. The importance of interaction and production is developed more intensively in journalist training, although the greatest professional demands are in the technological dimension (Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al., 2020).

Audience Assessment of News Quality Presentation

Audiences need information that can be easily received and is useful for life. Audiences who come from various elements of society assess the quality of the news produced and presented on the screen, paying great attention to a neat and confident appearance, conveying news directly with clear intonation, as well as being agile in reporting and completely explaining the chronology of the news. Apart from that, television media also needs to report public policies, especially in the fields of public transportation for the benefit of society and trade and economy, to attract investment from the business world. The audience agreed that journalists, in maintaining the quality of their news, always cooperate with the government and help maintain the stability and security of the country through the news they broadcast. The application of journalism is expected to be able to encourage public intelligence to participate in building the nation with all its diversity and excellence, but on the other hand, journalists must prevent uniformity of views without providing sufficient space for comparisons (Winarto 2020). Apart from that, the news presented contains content that attracts the public's attention. The application of journalism is expected to be able to encourage public intelligence to participate in building the nation with all its diversity and excellence, but on the other hand, journalists must prevent uniformity of views without providing sufficient space for comparisons (Winarto, 2020).

Table 5: Audience assessment of news quality

Indicator	Very low		Low		High		Very high	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
The media broadcasts news in a language that is easy for the public to understand.	0	0	0	0	7	6,4	103	93,6
Journalists report the news with a clear intonation.	0	0	0	0	5	4,5	105	9,5
Journalists appear confident when delivering news through the screen.	0	0	0	0	7	6,4	103	93,6
Journalists convey news in sentences that are easy for viewers to understand.	1	0,9	25	22,7	17	15,5	67	60,9
Television journalists appear neat when reading the news on the screen.	0	0	0	0	1	0,9	109	99,1
The news conveyed by journalists is reality.	0	0	1	0,9	14	12,7	95	86,4
The news broadcast by television journalists is very accurate, so the public trusts it.	0	0	2	1,8	14	12,7	94	85,5
The news delivered by television journalists is objective, not tendentious.	2	1,8	32	29,1	33	30	43	39,1
The news content broadcast on television media is a variety of events that attract public attention.	0	0	0	0	8	7,3	102	92,7

Indicator	Very low		Low		High		Very high	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Television journalists are deft in reporting.	0	0	0	0	5	4,5	105	95,5
Television journalists present news with in-depth interviews with the perpetrators of the events.	0	0	1	0,9	13	11,8	96	87,3
Investigative news broadcasts on television media attracted the attention of residents.	0	0	0	0	7	6,4	103	93,6
The news broadcast on television does not contain any elements of rumor.	3	2,7	2	1,8	12	10,9	93	84,5
The news that I make shows the location where a case occurred.	1	0,9	0	0	7	6,4	102	92,7
The news broadcast includes information on the identity of the perpetrator of the incident	1	0,9	0	0	15	13,6	94	85,5
The news conveyed is written in a complete series of events.	1	0,9	0	0	5	4,5	104	94,5
The news about an event that is conveyed is written in an orderly manner so that the public knows the chronology.	2	1,8	0	0	7	6,4	101	91,8
News about the existence of public transportation services is informed to the public using public transportation.	0	0	2	1,8	9	8,2	99	90
The news about changes in routes for public transportation that was broadcast was felt to be useful by the public.	0	0	3	2,7	4	3,6	103	93,6
News is broadcast on television media as a government partner inviting the public to take part in maintaining the security and stability of the country.	0	0	4	3,6	3	2,7	103	93,6
The news broadcast by television media does not contain elements of hatred that could trigger conflict.	0	0	5	4,5	11	10	94	85,5
News about the existence of public policies in the trade sector needs to be disseminated to the public.	1	0,9	0	0	1	0,9	108	98,2
Sustainable development programs are broadcast transparently to the public.	0	0	2	1,8	6	5,5	102	92,7
People like news that shows the success of development programs in various sectors.	0	0	1	0,9	10	9,1	99	90
The news content that is broadcast pays attention to interests that concern the livelihoods of many people.	2	1,8	20	18,2	15	13,6	73	66,4
The news broadcast raises issues surrounding social changes in life in society	0	0	1	0,9	9	8,2	100	90,9
Economic news attracts attention because it can be a reference for business people to invest.	0	0	2	1,8	3	2,7	105	95,5

Based on Table 5, it is known that the highest assessment of news quality was found in the indicators of television journalists appearing neat when reading news on the screen (99.1 %) and news that public policies in the trade sector need to be disseminated to the public (98.2%). The implementation of journalism is expected to be able to encourage public intelligence to participate in building the nation with all its diversity and excellence, but on the other hand, journalists must prevent uniformity of views without providing sufficient room for comparison (Winarto, 2020).

Apart from that, the media must maintain the quality of the news, starting with the topics presented and interesting audio and video, so that it can attract the attention of a large audience. Shailendra and Prakash (2008) said that if development is to be accelerated, then provide complete, fastest, most up-to-date, and relevant information to public representatives elected by the people. The role of the news media is to achieve legitimacy and create positive perceptions in the eyes of the public (Gaol et al., 2020).

In assessing the quality of voice intonation, it was considered low when reading the news (9.5%). Lacy and Rosenstiel (2015) said that news content can have quality journalistic elements based on the journalist's perspective, and news audiences can produce quality evaluations because of different desires and needs for information. Linguistic or formal features, bylines, sources, subjective expressions, and similarity of articles are influential (Choi et al., 2021).

Based on the results of interviews with news observers, the researcher believes that news quality is influenced by the intervention and adaptation of media technology. In implementing his duties and role as a development journalist, he must adhere to the journalistic code of ethics as regulated in Law No. 40 of 1999 concerning the press. Article 5 also states that journalists present news in a balanced and fair manner, prioritizing accuracy over speed and not mixing facts and opinions. Television and media journalists are sometimes found to have violated the code of ethics due to intervention from the government and media conglomerates. Journalists comply with guidelines that refer to the Press Law as guidelines, corridors, and work signs for broadcasters (Winora et al., 2021).

The press is tasked with presenting news based on objective data according to facts in the field, providing accurate information, upholding professionalism by always adhering to the Press Law, and adhering to the journalistic code of ethics (Muannas et al., 2021). The process of establishing media professionalism and implementing the Journalistic Code of Ethics revealed that the process of establishing media professionalism has not gone well, and there are still many violations. The problem of decreasing quality is also caused by enthusiastic audiences raising ratings for the media, causing news quality to only be measured based on the number of viewers. When the number of viewers becomes a barometer of news quality, the media pursues rating shares to determine the quality of their news, no longer referring to journalistic competency standards.

The rating share barometer triggers mainstream media to try to get several viewers by broadcasting popular and shocking news to meet the audience's market consumption. It is known that the quality of television programs shows that the quality of the program shows satisfaction, and watching satisfaction will provide loyalty (Sudarmawan, 2020). Apart from that, the quality of news decreases due to intervention from stakeholders, so the information presented is considered unbalanced or neutral. News quality relates to the verification of misinformation, audience attraction, and engagement.

The role of television newsrooms is potentially positive, and journalists' social media is beneficial to audience engagement, indicating a lack of time, tools, strategies, and training

causes a decline in the quality of the role of social media journalists, and their role can conquer barriers to news channels (Guo & Volz, 2021; Yousuf Humaid Yousufi et al., 2019).

On the other hand, community representatives and media monitoring institutions highlighted and assessed a decline in the quality of news produced by television journalists based on its broadcast. Based on the results of interviews with community representatives, managers, and administrators of independent and dependent media organizations, the causes of low news quality are (1) complaints of violations from the Indonesian Broadcasting Institution; (2) complaints from the public; (3) less attractive news packaging; (4) competition on social media with netizen journalism who create opinions and post trust; (5) less in-depth news analysis; and (6) intervention from stakeholders or certain institutions. (7) lack of cross-checking; (8) lack of verification and validation; (9) the press is still excessive in reporting; (10) broadcasts that violate moral norms. (11) liberalization of media establishments, (12) lack of internal media coaching, (12) lack of creativity in the digital era; (13) hampered by the mindset of journalists who find it difficult to face rapid changes in media technology; (14) lack of rewards given by management to journalists. The credibility of online media news influences the trust of people who have low levels of trust, tending to prefer non-mainstream news sources, such as social media and blogs, while digital providers are more likely to engage in various forms of online news participation (Fletcher & Park, 2017). The presentation of quality news must have complete news value, and the truth does not refer to online media (Lestari, 2017).

The cause of the decline in reporting value is anticipated by media organizations, which are giving in the form of training, rewards, supervising news direction policies, improving news content writing, and forming a digital media business.

CONCLUSION

Journalist competence plays an important role in presenting quality news and influencing the audience. Journalists who have professional competence, good communication skills, in-depth media knowledge, and a strong social orientation are considered capable of producing accurate news and having an impact on improving people's lives. Journalists need to maintain integrity, carry out verification, and pay attention to the needs and aspirations of the community when presenting news.

Collaboration between journalists, the media, and the public is needed to improve the quality of news and ensure that development messages are conveyed accurately, although stakeholder intervention, ethical violations, and the dynamics of media technology can affect the quality of the news. With professional expertise, effective communication skills, in-depth knowledge of media, and social awareness as journalists, journalists can present informative and impactful news. Journalist competence not only includes professional and technical aspects but also broad social responsibilities in conveying correct and relevant information to the public. Journalists' efforts to maintain the quality of news are increasingly important, considering the role of the press as a guardian of democracy, supporting development programs, and voicing people's aspirations, in addition to monitoring power.

The audience assessed the presentation of the news by assessing the quality of the news produced and presented, paying great attention to a neat and confident appearance, conveying the news directly with clear intonation, and being agile in reporting and explaining the chronology in full. From the news. On the other hand, independent and dependent media institutions found factors that influenced the decline in news quality due to intervention from stakeholders, violations of ethical codes, as well as economic dynamics and media technology.

The public also has a role in determining the quality of news by influencing demand for information that is easily accessible and useful. Cooperation between journalists, the media, and the public is needed to improve the quality of news and ensure that the content conveyed is relevant, accurate, transparent, and forgiving for people's lives. On the other hand, to meet development information needs, the public expects quality news in terms of content and benefits.

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